

ANALYSIS OF THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND NUTRITIONAL VALUE OF GRAIN RAW MATERIALS FOR THE PRODUCTION OF BABY FOOD

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7450965>

Annotation: The study of the nutrition problems of children over one-year-old, as well as the proper organization of nutrition in preschool and school institutions is an urgent task of today. The intensity of the child's growth entails the intensity of metabolic processes, an increase in energy costs, morphological and functional improvement of the respiratory organs, cardiovascular, digestive and other systems. The neuropsychic system undergoes global changes associated with obtaining a large amount of information.

Key words: the nutrition problems, children, intensity, metabolic processes, energy costs, morphological and functional improvement, respiratory organs

INTRODUCTION

The study of the nutrition problems of children over one year old, as well as the proper organization of nutrition in preschool and school institutions is an urgent task of today. The intensity of the child's growth entails the intensity of metabolic processes, an increase in energy costs, morphological and functional improvement of the respiratory organs, cardiovascular, digestive and other systems. The neuropsychic system undergoes global changes associated with obtaining a large amount of information.

Various combinations of grain components in combination with fruit, vegetable and berry additives, as well as the use of modern production technologies, make it possible to significantly expand the range of high-quality, biologically complete and balanced products for baby food at various stages of growth. The State Academy of Sciences for 2013-2020 conducts research on the development of grain-based products with the introduction of fruit, vegetable and berry components for children over one-year-old, as well as preschool and school age. The products will take into account the rational and balanced composition of the nutriment, taking into account the age of the child. The current stage of research includes the selection of raw materials and the assessment of its nutritional value based on the analysis of calculated data on the chemical composition of

grain raw materials, as well as fruit, vegetable and berry components. This article is devoted to the analysis of the chemical composition of nine grain crops, seven of which are traditionally used as raw materials in the production of baby food. There are also such crops as triticale and amaranth, which have recently been gaining popularity [1-6].

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The purpose of the work is to expand the range and increase the nutritional value of the products being developed by combining rarely used types of grain raw materials with natural fruit, vegetable and berry components. The nutritional value of food is determined by the content of proteins, fats and carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals and other biologically active compounds in them. Data on the content of individual amino acids, fatty acids, vitamins, macro- and microelements significantly expand our understanding of the biological value of food, help to understand the biochemical processes of digestion. Table 1 provides data on the composition of the grain of the crops in question in terms of the content of the main components of food in it. The content of grain nutrients is subject to large fluctuations depending on many factors: varieties, climatic conditions of growth, agrochemical conditions of cultivation, etc. Carbohydrates are the main source of energy, providing up to 50-60% of the total caloric content of the diet. And the main sources of carbohydrates are vegetable, including grain products. By chemical composition, the grains of all cereals belong to the group of starchy vegetable raw materials, since the digestible carbohydrates in them are mainly starch and contain it in the range from 36% (oats) to 50-70% (the remaining grains); also contains about 1% sucrose and a small amount of glucose, fructose, raffinose, maltose and stachyose [7, 8].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When studying and analyzing the chemical composition of the crops under consideration, it should be noted that the data presented in various literary sources differ from each other. This is due both to the improvement of technologies and methods of their production, and the difference in the properties of the raw materials under study – both by varieties and by cultivation territories (data from the US Department of Agriculture were used in the review). The results of the analysis of calculated data on the chemical composition of raw materials can be used in the preparation of balanced diets, taking into account the age and individual characteristics of the body, as well as the prevention and treatment of certain diseases in the development of new full-

fledged food products. When developing diets, it is necessary to strive for their maximum diversity and include all food groups in their composition. Along with a full-fledged amino acid and vitamin composition, the composition of the children's nutriome should be optimal in terms of its energy value and the amount of other nutrients, primarily irreplaceable. The combined use of grain raw materials can make up for the lack of high-grade and low-grade proteins, lipid complex, as well as mineral and biologically active substances and, as a result, will be the most nutritious and useful. A mandatory requirement in this case is a balance between all essential and non-essential nutrition factors, since a violation of this principle can cause a relative lack of one of the food components.

CONCLUSION

Even under the condition of its adequate absolute level in the diet. Amaranth grain, when used in a mixture with other grain crops, can become a valuable food product in the children's nutriome, due to the mutual enrichment of nutrients to cover the deficiency of protein and lipid components and increase the biological and nutritional value of the diet. Further work on the study of the properties of grain products, as well as fruit, vegetable and berry raw materials will allow us to develop a new high-quality balanced product that has no analogues in its biological and nutritional value. It can be used in the diet of children over a year old, as well as preschool and school age.

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